

Research to inform asylum policy from the University of York, Department of Sociology.

FREEDOM OF RELIGION OR BELIEF FOR ALL:

Recognising and protecting the non-Religious in the asylum system

Dr Lucy Potter, University of York, in collaboration with Humanists UK, January 2025

Summary

- Non-religious ‘apostates’—individuals who leave or renounce their religion—face systemic disadvantages when seeking asylum in the UK.
- While protected in principle by the 1951 Refugee Convention and international human rights law, these claimants risk being failed by Refugee Status Determination (RSD) processes structured around religious belief and practice. Specifically, current decision-making policies for religion-based claims are orientated around religious conversion frameworks, which overlook the distinct identities and unique persecution risks faced by non-religious individuals.
- Drawing on three years of qualitative research, this brief identifies barriers to protection including: biased credibility assessments, unrealistic evidentiary demands, and limited FoRB knowledge and training among Home Office officials, resulting in misguided and inappropriate asylum interview questioning.

Recommendations for policy

For the government’s asylum policymakers:

1. Update Asylum Policies and Country Guidance

Update and expand Asylum Policy Instructions (APIs) and Country Policy and Information Notes (CPINs) to explicitly recognise non-religious persecution and clearly distinguish these cases from broader guidance on religious belief.

2. Training for Non-Religious Apostasy

Train Home Office officials on the non-linear nature of belief change and ensure accurate, disaggregated recording of asylum claims based on non-religion.

3. Revise Credibility Guidance

Update credibility guidance to reflect non-religious beliefs and strengthen consistent application of legal standards.

4. Adjust Evidential Burden

Adjust evidential requirements to ensure lack of objective evidence does not disadvantage claimants and ensure trauma-informed questioning.

5. Improve Interpreter Practices

Enhance vetting procedures and provide transcripts with a correction period. Provide interpreters with a dedicated information pack covering the nuances of non-religious interpretation.

6. Embed Fair and Consistent Decision-Making

Reduce decision-making bias alongside other reforms to ensure a fair and consistent asylum system.

7. Strengthen Training and Knowledge

Establish ongoing FoRB-focused training for all Home Office staff and strengthen engagement with expert civil-society organisations.

Context of the research

*Can you name philosophers who were humanists?
What are the beliefs and thoughts of prominent non-religious thinkers?
Do you drink alcohol and have you ever eaten pork?*

These are all questions apostates – people who have left religion – have reported being asked during their asylum interviews with the UK Home Office. However, these questions often have no relation to the experiences of someone who has left their faith and thus fall short at accurately assessing whether an individual has a fear of persecution on the basis of this.

This research finds that despite the standards established in international human rights protections of Freedom of Religion or Belief (FoRB) and national asylum policies, apostate asylum seekers must work harder to prove their non-religiosity to decision-makers due to bureaucratic hurdles, encountering bias, contradictions between policy and practice and a lack of designated FoRB training.

Despite repeated calls from Humanists UK to improve policy and practice on non-religious claims, there has been little corresponding action to improve policy or practice in the UK.

Labour pledges to restore order to the asylum system so it operates 'swiftly, firmly and fairly'. On 17 November, the Home Secretary announced renewed asylum reforms. Although they make no direct reference to non-religious asylum claims, they are likely to have significant implications for this area of work.

The Non-Religious Apostates

For many non-religious people who seek asylum, becoming an apostate is not a single event but a deeply personal and gradual process, shaped by their historical, social, cultural and political backgrounds. As such, fleeing persecution on these grounds is multifaceted entailing shifts in worldviews, beliefs and involves profound emotional transformation.

Apostates who become non-religious include a range of identities, such as atheists, agnostics, humanists, freethinkers, rationalists and many more. Some may not identify with a particular label, or change labels over time. Non-religious identities are also understood differently outside the UK, as not all forms of nonbelief, non-religion, or atheism are identical.

The majority of countries globally restrict the right to Freedom of Religion or Belief (FoRB) to varying degrees; the largest risk posed for the non-religious are blasphemy and/or apostasy laws.

- 12 countries impose the death penalty for apostasy;
- 60 countries enforce prison sentences for both blasphemy and/or apostasy;
- 19 countries impose fines or administrative sanctions for blasphemy.

The Home Office Building, London

Findings Summary

1. Policy and Guidance Gaps

Apostate asylum claims are poorly addressed in current asylum policy. The non-religious are often not recognised or treated as distinct belief systems from other religion-based claimants.

2. Misunderstandings of Apostasy

Apostate claimants feel misunderstood and insufficiently recognised, revealing a gap between lived experience and institutional expectations.

3. Bias in Credibility Assessments

Current assessments favour demonstrable or 'fixed' expressions of belief. Interview practices can reflect Western assumptions of identity.

4. Evidential Burden & Unrealistic Expectations

Applicants face high burdens to prove identities that are not externally visible, often being asked to recall detailed early-life experiences or provide logical proofs of belief rejection.

5. Interpreter Accuracy and Bias

Interpreters may provide inaccurate translations due to personal bias or fear, and applicants may distrust interpreters from their own communities.

6. Perceived Culture of Scepticism

Despite official assurances, claimants and advocates report recurring scepticism towards non-religious claims which can erode trust and impact fair and impartial decision-making.

7. Limited FoRB Training

Although specific FoRB training was previously developed, it has not been consistently implemented or continued, resulting in ongoing gaps in knowledge and practice.

Further information

Contact the researcher:

Dr Lucy Potter
lucy.potter@york.ac.uk

DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/20424587>